

A HIERARCHICAL MULTISCALE MODEL FOR IN-PLANE MECHANICAL STRENGTH OF STITCHED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: The contribution attempts to model the alteration of the in-plane elastic properties in laminates caused by stitching. The distortion of in-plane fibers is considered to be the main reason that influences the in-plane mechanical properties. The fiber distortion model is proposed to characterize the fiber misalignment and the fiber content concentration caused by stitching. The undistorted region, the fiber distortion region, the resin-rich pocket and the through-thickness reinforcement section are taken into account. The fiber misalignment and the inhomogeneous fiber content caused by stitching have been formulated by introducing two parameters, i.e. distortion width w and maximum misalignment ϕ_0 . Then the in-plane strength of the stitched composite laminate are formulated based on the assumption that the stitched laminate fails when the average value of the ratio of longitudinal stress to strength in the 0-deg lamina over a characteristic length, l_0 , away from the stitch hole is equal to the unit.

KEYWORDS: Stitching, fiber distortion, in-plane strength, micromechanics.

INTRODUCTION

Stitched composite laminates have three-dimensional fiber architectures that the through-the-thickness direction is strengthened through the stitching technology in contrast to traditional laminates with a two-dimensional fiber structure. The introduction of the through-the-thickness reinforcements can substantially improve the through-the-thickness properties of laminates [1][2]. On the other hand, the stitches force the in-plane fibers to move away, making the local damages occurred. The fiber orientation and fiber content in the stitched composite laminate vary in the regions affected by the stitching, and the resin-rich pocket appears during the impregnation of the resin. In this paper, the fiber distortion model (FDM) will be proposed to describe the inhomogeneous material properties of the stitched composite laminate. The fiber orientation, fiber volume fraction and the in-plane strength of the stitched composite laminate are formulated.

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE FIBER DISTORTION

Assume the stitches are periodically distributed in the laminate plane, illustrated in Fig.1. The laminate coordinate system $x-y$ is used where the x - and y -axes are parallel to and perpendicular to the fibers in the 0°-plies, respectively. Each lamina in the laminate is referred to its own coordinate system, $X-Y$, where the X -axis is parallel to the undistorted fiber direction. In order to isolate the changes in properties due to stitching we assume there is an equivalent unstitched laminate, which is, except for the stitches, the same as the stitched laminate in ply orientation, in stacking sequence, in gross fiber content and in size of

specimen. The fiber distortion is assumed solely due to stitching. The influence of laminate configuration on the distortions in individual plies is ignored, namely, the localized distortions

Fig.1, Arrangement of stitches in a laminate

of the θ -deg angle-ply in the laminate can be represented by those of the 0-deg ply with a rotation of the θ -degree. Therefore, without loss of generality we consider a unidirectional lamina in the stitched composite laminate, which could be divided into such four domains as the undistorted region, the fiber distortion region, the resin-rich pocket and the through-thickness reinforcement section. In the undistorted region the fibers are not altered by stitches. In contrast the thread forces fibers in the distortion region to bend and move aside, resulting in fiber misalignment as well as inhomogeneous fiber volume fraction. The through-thickness reinforcement region is assumed circular with a radius R equal to stitch thread diameter. Because of the symmetry a quarter of the unit cell shown in Fig.2 is analyzed. We may make the following hypotheses:

Fig.2, A quarter of the unit cell of a lamina in the stitched laminate

1. Fibers in the distortion zone are approximately straight. The linear equation of a fiber is

$$Y = -X\phi + Y_0 \tag{1}$$

where Y_0 is the Y -coordinate of the intersection of the fiber and the Y -axis, ϕ the angle between the fiber and X -axis.

2. Angular misalignment of fibers varies from fiber to fiber in the distortion region with a maximum value given by angle, ϕ_0 , on the edge of stitch. The fiber misalignment decreases with an increasing distance away from the stitch, disappearing at some distance, w . For simplicity the fiber misalignment of fibers is assumed to follow a liner variation along the Y -axis, i.e.

$$\phi = \phi_0 \left(1 - \frac{Y_0 - R}{w}\right) \quad (2)$$

where w is the width of the fiber distortion zone at $X=0$.

3. The fiber, which has a maximum misalignment given by angle, ϕ_0 , defines the inner boundary of the distortion region with the resin-rich pocket. The outer boundary of the fiber distortion zone is elliptical and defined by

$$\frac{(X_b \phi_0)^2}{R^2} + \frac{Y_b^2}{(w+R)^2} = 1 \quad (3)$$

where (X_b, Y_b) is the coordinate of a point on the elliptical boundary.

Consequently the fiber volume fraction in the distorted region can be expressed by

$$f(X, Y) = \frac{f_0 w}{w + X\phi_0} (1 + g(X, Y)) \quad (4)$$

where f_0 is the fiber volume fraction in the undistorted region, $g(X, Y)$, an explicit function, is not given here due to the space limitation. Now the fiber misalignment and the inhomogeneous fiber volume fraction caused by stitching have been determined at any point within the fiber distortion region. In the formulae two parameters, namely distortion width, w , and maximum misalignment, ϕ_0 , need to be determined experimentally. The micromechanical relationships between the elastic properties and the fiber volume fraction can be used to predict the spatial variation of the elastic constants of unidirectional laminates and multidirectional laminates around the stitch.

INHOMOGENEOUS STRESSES IN STITCHED LAMINATES

Consider a stitched composite laminate that is subjected to a uniaxial tensile loading in the x -direction. The through-the-thickness reinforcement regions, which are usually made from carbon, glass or Kevlar yarns, have a high longitudinal tensile strength but the low transverse strength. From the conservative point of view one may ignore the strength of the stitch regions which could be considered to be circular holes with a diameter $2R$ equal to twice the size of stitch thread. Outside the through-the-thickness reinforcement regions the laminate is modeled as an anisotropic plane stress plate with the spatially varying effective properties. The stitch holes will cause local stress concentration. The non-uniform elastic properties also alter the distribution of both ply stress and laminate stress around the stitches. Here the two-dimensional (2D) finite element method along is used to predict such inhomogeneous stress distribution.

FAILURE CRITERION FOR STITCHED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

The experimental evidences indicated that the failure of stitched laminates started from the stitch boundary due to the high stress concentration around the stitches. Since the transverse strength of the through-the-thickness reinforcement is very low the stitch regions could be considered to be small circular holes. The inhomogeneous fiber content and the fiber misalignment are two important factors, amongst others, which causes the distinction of the stitched laminates from the traditional laminates. It is assumed that the stitched laminate fails when the average value of the ratio of longitudinal stress to strength in the 0-deg lamina over a characteristic length away from the stitch hole is equal to the unit. The mathematical express for the failure criterion is given by

$$\frac{1}{l_0} \int_R^{R+l_0} \frac{\sigma_1^{(0)}(0, y)}{F(0, y)} dy \geq 1 \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma_1^{(0)}$ and F are longitudinal stress and strength of the 0-deg plies at a local point. The characteristic length, l_0 , is a composite material constant independent of the laminate configuration, the size of hole and the stitching parameters. The ply stress $\sigma_1^{(0)}$ can be computed by using the constitutive equation of the 0-deg lamina at a local point referred to material principle axes. The laminate strain is evaluated by utilizing the finite element analysis. The longitudinal strength of the 0°- lamina at a local point, F , can be estimated by the rule-of-mixture, i.e.

$$F(x, y) = F_f \left(f(x, y) + \frac{E_m}{E_f} (1 - f(x, y)) \right) \quad (6)$$

where F_f , f , E_f , E_m are the ultimate tensile strength of the fiber, the fiber volume fraction, the longitudinal Young's modulus of the fiber, Young's modulus of the matrix, respectively. Remember the fact that the fiber content changes from point to point, the strength of the 0°- lamina will vary spatially, i.e. $F(x, y)$.

The overall strength of the stitched laminate is influenced by two opposite factors. On the one hand the stress concentration and the fiber misalignment caused by stitching reduce the laminate strength. On the other hand the fiber content concentration induced by stitching will make composite stronger. The factors compete to determine whether the stitch reduces or increases the strength.

RESULTS

For illustration the carbon/epoxy material system called T300/QY9512 given in reference [3] is considered, which has the properties of constituents:

$$E_{f1} = 221GPa, E_{f2} = 13.8GPa, G_{f1} = 9.0GPa, G_{f2} = 4.8GPa, \nu_{f12} = 0.2, \nu_{f21} = 0.25, \\ E_m = 3.4GPa, \nu_m = 0.3, f_0 = 0.6.$$

In order to verify the accuracy of the present model and to demonstrate its predictability, we compare the predictions of the new theory with the experimental data for the [0/45/0/-

45/90/45/0/-45]2s T300/QY9512 composite laminate stitched by Kevlar 29 yarn, $R = 1500$ denier (0.19 mm). Two stitching directions parallel to and perpendicular to the fibers in the 0-

Stitch step and space	Tensile strength in x -direction (MPa)			
	Stitching parallel to 0-ply		Stitching normal to 0-ply	
	Experiment	Prediction	Experiment	Prediction
Unstitched	585.18	--	585.18	--
3mm*3mm	514.21	514.22	481.43	514.22
3mm*5mm	500.70	564.35	--	448.48
8mm*5mm	532.76	437.01	536.77	516.57
10mm*10mm	505.94	432.48	512.80	432.48

deg plies along with the four stitch densities with step and space, i.e. 3mm*3mm, 3mm*5mm, 8mm*5mm and 10mm*10mm are considered, making eight different stitched laminate specimens. The stitched laminates are subjected to a uni-axial tensile loading in the x -direction parallel to the fibers of the 0-deg plies. It is assumed the maximum misalignment angle, $\phi_0 = 10^\circ$ and distortion width, $w = 1$ mm. The characteristic length, l_0 , in the present model is determined by using the strength data of the laminate specimen stitched parallel to 0°-ply with stitch density 3*3. Then, the same value of $l_0 = 0.555$ (mm), is used to predict the tensile strength of the laminate specimens with the other stitching parameters. The comparison between the predicted values and the experimental data is illustrated in the table, showing a reasonable agreement.

Fig. 3 Spatial variation of the longitudinal ply strength

The substantial enhancement of the ply strength due to the fiber content concentration induced by stitching is illustrated in Fig.3 where the enhanced strength at a local point normalized by the unmodified tensile strength, $F(0, y)/F_0$, is plotted as a function of y . However the value

of the stitch parameters such as the stitch step and stitch space has a negligible effect on the magnitude of the increase in the strength. Fig. 4 shows the effects of the stitch step on the 0° -ply stress concentration in the stitched composite laminates with the unchanged stitch space

Fig. 4 Influence of stitch step on the 0° -ply stress concentration

(3mm) and four stitch steps (3, 5, 8, 10 mm). The 0° -ply stress concentration gets higher with the decreasing stitch step. Fig. 5 illustrates the influence of the stitch space on the 0° -ply stress concentration in the stitched composite laminates with the unchanged stitch step (5mm) and four stitch spaces (3, 5, 8, 10 mm). Conversely the 0° -ply stress concentration gets smaller with the decreases of the stitch space. Consequently the tensile strength of the stitched

Fig. 5 Influence of stitch space on the 0° -ply stress concentration

laminates will decrease and increase with a decreasing stitch step and a decreasing space, respectively.

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